

Toward Safe and Sustainable Batteries: $\text{Na}_4\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ as a Low-Cost Cathode for Rechargeable Aqueous Na-Ion Batteries

Antonio J. Fernández-Ropero,^{†,§} Maider Zarrabeitia,^{†,‡} Marine Reynaud,[†] Teófilo Rojo,^{†,‡} Montse Casas-Cabanas^{*,†}

[†] CIC energiGUNE, Parque Tecnológico de Álava, Albert Einstein 48, ED.CIC, 01510 Miñano, Spain

[‡] Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Universidad del País Vasco UPV/EHU, P.O. Box. 644, 48080 Leioa, Spain

ABSTRACT:

The electrochemical properties of $\text{Na}_4\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ in aqueous and organic electrolyte are compared under similar conditions. $\text{Na}_4\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ is able to deliver almost the same capacity in both types of electrolytes despite the smaller electrochemical window entailed by the aqueous one. As shown by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), this is possible thanks to the lower overpotential that this material exhibits in aqueous electrolyte. It is shown here that the main contribution to overpotential in organic electrolyte mainly originates from a SPI (Solid Permeable Interphase) layer formed below 3.5 V vs Na^+/Na that acts as a blocking layer and hinders Na^+ diffusion and that is absent in aqueous electrolyte. Overall, the obtained results highlight the positive attributes of using low-cost and environmentally friendly aqueous electrolytes and the challenges to be overcome in terms of air and moisture stability of the studied material.

INTRODUCTION

Na-ion batteries (NIBs) are considered an attractive alternative to Li-ion batteries (LIBs) due to the lower cost and wider abundance of sodium as compared to lithium.¹⁻³ Additionally, the use of aqueous electrolytes instead of organic ones in NIBs offers the possibility to design cost-effective, safe, and environmentally friendly devices. Aqueous NIBs are thus particularly attractive for applications where cost prevails over energy density, this latter aspect being generally penalized by the narrow electrochemical stability window of water.⁴

Several families of materials have been investigated in aqueous Na-based electrolytes: NASICON-type $\text{NaTi}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ ^{5,6} and isostructural $\text{Na}_3\text{MgTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ ⁷ as negative electrodes or NASICON-type $\text{Na}_3\text{MnTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ ⁸ and $\text{Na}_2\text{VTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ ⁹ which have been implemented in symmetric cells. Regarding positive electrodes, the most studied materials belong to three different families: oxides, as the λ - MnO_2 ⁴ spinel and several tunnel materials as $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ ¹⁰ and $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ ¹¹ Prussian-blue^{12,13} and analogues;^{14,15} and polyanionic compounds such as $\text{Na}_2\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7$ ¹⁶ and NaFePO_4 .¹⁷

Among the later, iron- and manganese-based materials are the most attractive positive electrode materials for aqueous NIBs in terms of cost and low toxicity,¹⁸ and phosphates and pyrophosphates are particularly promising because of the high cycling stability obtained in organic electrolytes.^{1,19} Several of them were evaluated as positive electrode materials for aqueous NIBs over the past few years. $\text{Na}_2\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7$ ¹⁶ was shown

44 to deliver a specific capacity of 58 mAh g⁻¹ and a capacity retention of 86% after 300
45 cycles with an average voltage of 2.76 V vs Na⁺/Na (0.05 V vs SHE) at 1C.

46 Alternatively, olivine NaFePO₄¹⁷ delivers a specific capacity of 70 mAh g⁻¹ with an
47 average voltage of 2.95 V vs Na⁺/Na (0.24 V vs SHE) and a good cycling stability at 1C
48 using a 1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution as the electrolyte. This material has to be obtained
49 from electrochemical or chemical delithiation and sodiation of the olivine LiFePO₄,^{20,21}
50 which is a common commercialized cathode for LIBs, since its direct synthesis would
51 lead to the thermodynamically stable maricite polymorph. Na₂FePO₄F²² has not been
52 tested in aqueous electrolyte although it also operates within its stability window
53 because its synthesis requires complex and costly procedures which make it unattractive
54 for the targeted low-cost applications of aqueous NIBs. In contrast, Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇
55 represents a more attractive option since (i) it can be directly obtained by a solid-state
56 route at relatively low temperature, (ii) it operates at a suitable potential for aqueous
57 electrolytes (3.0 V vs Na⁺/Na / 0.29 V vs SHE), and (iii) it presents good electrochemical
58 performances in terms of rate capability and capacity in organic electrolytes^{23,24} and, as
59 shown herein, in aqueous electrolyte. In this work, the electrochemical properties of
60 Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ are analyzed using a 1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution as the electrolyte
61 and are compared to its performance in an organic electrolyte under similar conditions.
62 The air stability of the material, the origin of the low overpotential in aqueous
63 electrolyte, and the stability of the material in aqueous solution have been thoroughly
64 analysed using several techniques including powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD),
65 electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS),
66 and inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES).

67 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

68 Synthesis of Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇. Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ was synthesized via a conventional
69 two-step solid-state route using 2.24 g of Na₄P₂O₇ (95%, Aldrich), 4.36 g of FeC₂O₄·2H₂O
70 (99%, Aldrich), and 1.87 g of (NH₄)₂HPO₄ (98%, Aldrich) as precursors.²³ This
71 stoichiometric mixture of precursors was thoroughly ground using a Fritsch Mill
72 pulverizette 5 classic line equipment at 200 rpm for 24 h in an acetone suspension (25
73 mL for the cited amount). The wet milling was required to avoid the formation of
74 impurities thanks to a better mixing of precursors (see Figure S1). The acetone was dried
75 at 60 °C, and the recovered powder mixture was then heated at 300 °C for 6 h under N₂
76 flow. In a second step, 5 wt% of black conductive additive (Super C65, TIMCAL) was
77 added to the calcined precursor mixture and wet-milled for 1 h (1 g of mix in 40 mL of
78 acetone). The resulting mixture was then pelletized (2 t cm⁻² for 0.5 g cm⁻²) and
79 annealed at 500 °C for 12 h under N₂ flow. Hereafter the composition of the powder will
80 be referred to as Na_{4-δ}Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ because the samples are slightly oxidized upon air
81 exposure (see below), while the electrode composition will be referred as Na₄₋
82 _xFe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ (0 ≤ x ≤ 3) in order to take into account the variation in Na concentration
83 during battery operation.

84 Structural and Chemical Characterization. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) data were
85 recorded using a Bruker D8 Discover instrument with monochromatic copper radiation
86 (λCu,Kα1 = 1.54056 Å) and were refined using the FullProf Suite software.^{25,26} The
87 refinement of the XRD pattern of the asprepared phase of Na_{4-δ}Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ was

88 performed using Rietveld's method, while the refinements of the XRD patterns of the
89 aged samples were done by Le Bail method. Kim et al. for $\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ obtained
90 by chemical desodiation using NO_2BF_4 .

91 The amount of remaining carbon in the sample after the synthesis process was
92 determined by a Thermo Scientific Mod. Flash EA 2000 CHNS/O elemental analyzer.

93 The viscosity measurement of a 1 M Na_2SO_4 aqueous solution was performed with an
94 Anton Paar Physica MCR301 Rheometer.

95 For the material's stability tests, inductively coupled plasma optical emission
96 spectroscopy (ICP-OES) of supernatants was carried out in an Ultima 2 Optical Emission
97 Spectrometer.

98 Electrochemical Characterization. $\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ electrodes were composed of 75
99 wt% of active material, 20 wt % of C65 as carbon additive, and 5 wt% of polyvinylidene
100 fluoride (PVDF) as binder (powder, Alfa Aesar). A slurry of the above-mentioned
101 composition dispersed in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP; 99.5% anhydrous, Sigma-
102 Aldrich) was deposited on stainless-steel current collector disks of 1 cm^2 and was dried
103 overnight at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under vacuum. The final mass loading for each electrode was 3 – 4
104 mg/cm^2 .

105 All electrochemical experiments were recorded in a Bio-Logic VMP3Multi-Channel
106 Potentiostat/Galvanostat.

107 Galvanostatic measurements in organic electrolyte (1 M NaClO_4 in EC:PC) were
108 performed in two electrode Swagelok-type half-cells with metallic sodium as counter
109 and reference electrodes. Aqueous cells were tested in three electrode Swagelok-type
110 cells with Ag/AgCl (3 M NaCl) as the reference electrode. To facilitate the comparison
111 between organic and aqueous media, the voltage values are herein reported vs Na^+/Na
112 taking into account that the potentials of Na^+/Na and Ag/AgCl (3 M NaCl) vs standard
113 hydrogen electrode (SHE) are -2.71 V and $+0.21\text{ V}$ respectively.^{3,27} Likewise, for the
114 comparison with results previously reported in aqueous electrolyte, the voltage of
115 aqueous cells is also expressed in V vs SHE. A solution of 1 M Na_2SO_4 (pH 6) was used as
116 aqueous electrolyte and activated carbon (AC; Norit DLC super30) was used as counter
117 electrode, in a weight ratio counter electrode (AC)/ working electrode
118 ($\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$) of 10:1 to ensure that the active material was the limiting electrode
119 and that the voltage variation of AC remains within the stability voltage window of the
120 aqueous electrolyte.¹⁷ Self-standing AC electrodes were prepared from a slurry with 5
121 wt% of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) in ethanol and were previously tested as
122 symmetric supercapacitor using three-electrode Swagelok-type cells (Figure S2).
123 Organic cells were assembled inside a glovebox with a dry Ar atmosphere, while all
124 aqueous cells were assembled inside a N_2 -containing glovebag (Aldrich) to avoid oxygen
125 since its presence would cause the oxidation of the electrode material during the
126 discharge process.²⁸ For the same reason, the aqueous electrolyte was previously
127 deoxygenated overnight with N_2 flow. Glass-fiber filters (Whatman, grade D) were used
128 as separator for all measured cells. For galvanostatic cycling, a specific current of 129
129 mA g^{-1} of active material (1C rate) was used for both organic and aqueous cells.

130 Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) experiments were performed in three-
131 electrode Swagelok-type cells using (i) metallic Na as both counter and reference

132 electrodes in organic electrolyte and (ii) AC and Ag/AgCl (3 M NaCl) as counter and
133 reference electrodes, respectively, in aqueous electrolyte. The impedance spectra were
134 recorded in the frequency range of 100 kHz-5 mHz at the end of the 20th, 30th, and 40th
135 charges (3.4 V vs Na⁺/Na / 0.69 V vs SHE) and discharges (2.5 V vs Na⁺/Na / -0.21 V vs
136 SHE) of the galvanostatic cycles after 1 h of equilibration time at constant potential in
137 order to reach the equilibrium conditions. The impedance spectra were fitted by
138 Boukamp's Equivalent Circuit software.²⁹

139 Surface Characterization. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to
140 study the electrodes surface composition in both organic and aqueous media at 3.4 V vs
141 Na⁺/Na (0.69 V vs SHE; charged state) and 2.5 V vs Na⁺/Na (-0.21 V vs SHE; discharged
142 state) using a Phoibos 150 XPS spectrometer and a nonmonochromatic Mg K α (h ν =
143 1253.6 eV) X-ray source. High-resolution scans were acquired at 100 W, 20 eV pass
144 energy, and 0.1 eV energy step. The electrodes were cycled in the previous described
145 Swagelok-type cells at a specific current of 129 mA g⁻¹ until the required voltage. The
146 recovered electrodes were rinsed with PC (organic cells) or distilled water (aqueous
147 cells) before being transferred to the XPS vacuum chamber by an Ar-filled transfer
148 system. The calibration was carried out taking into account the graphitic-like carbon
149 peak at 284.4 eV as reference since the graphitic species was based on Scofield's relative
150 sensitivity factors,³² and all elements were taken into account (Na, Fe, P, O, C, and F).
151 The fits were performed with the CasaXPS software³³ using a nonlinear Shirley-type
152 background, and a 70% Gaussian and 30% Lorentzian profile function, resulting in a
153 residual standard deviation (STD) lower than 1 for each fit.

154 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

155 Structural Characterization. Figure 1 shows the Rietveld refinement of the PXRD pattern
156 of the synthesized sample that ($a = 18.1047(5)$ Å, $b = 6.5348(2)$ Å, and $c = 10.6439(3)$ Å)
157 and atomic positions (Table S1) are in good agreement with those reported in the
158 literature²³ with the exception of the a parameter which is slightly larger in our work as
159 will be discussed later (see Table S2). The composition of the as prepared sample was
160 refined to Na_{4- δ} Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ with $\delta = 0.03$. The four Na positions were refined, but only
161 the Na2 site was partially unoccupied; this is in agreement with a previous report on this
162 material and its cobalt-based analogue in which Na2 is the first sodium to be
163 extracted.^{24,34} A secondary phase corresponding to maricite NaFePO₄ (Pnma space
164 group, with cell parameters: $a = 8.987(4)$ Å, $b = 6.856(3)$ Å, and $c = 5.043(2)$ Å) was
165 included in the refinement, accounting for 3.04 wt% of the crystalline phases of the
166 sample. On the other hand, 7.8 wt% of conducting carbon additive was found from the
167 elemental analysis after the synthesis process (see Table S3).

168

169
 170 Figure 1. Rietveld refinement of the PXRD pattern of the $\text{Na}_{3.97}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ pristine sample. Red, black,
 171 and blue lines represent the observed pattern, the calculated pattern, and the difference between them,
 172 respectively. Vertical bars represent the Bragg positions for $\text{Na}_{3.97}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (green) and maricite
 173 NaFePO_4 (violet, 3.04 wt% of the sample).

174
 175 Galvanostatic Experiments in Organic Electrolyte. The electrochemical performance of
 176 the material was first evaluated in organic electrolyte (1 M NaClO_4 in EC:PC) at 1C in the
 177 voltage window 4.3 – 1.8 V vs Na^+/Na (Figure 2a,c,d). Under these conditions, the
 178 material delivers 99 mAh g^{-1} of reversible capacity for the first discharge ($\Delta x = 2.3$ in
 179 $\text{Na}_{4-x}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$), although in the first charge the observed capacity was only 91 mAh
 180 g^{-1} ($\Delta x = 2.1$). The Coulombic efficiency in the first cycles was somewhat low ($\sim 95\%$) due
 181 to electrolyte oxidation but stabilized after 20 cycles ($\sim 97\%$; Figure 2d). The lower
 182 capacity delivered upon the first charge can be explained by a slight oxidation of the
 183 sample when exposed to air between the synthesis process and the electrochemical
 184 measurements, as confirmed from the Le Bail refinement of the PXRD pattern of a
 185 sample aged for one month under air (Figure S3). This sample exhibits a lower a cell
 186 parameter than the as-prepared sample (Table S2), whose estimated composition is
 187 $\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ with $\delta = 0.77$ obtained by linear interpolation of the a cell parameter
 188 (Vegard's law) of our pristine sample and the one reported by Kim et al. for
 189 $\text{Na}_1\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ obtained by chemical desodiation using NO_2BF_4 ²⁴ (Table S2).
 190 Therefore, the lower a cell parameter previously reported by Kim et al.²³ for
 191 $\text{Na}_4\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ may also indicate that their sample could have been slightly oxidized
 192 upon air exposure.

193

194 Figure 2. Galvanostatic profiles of $\text{Na}_{4-6}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ for the first two cycles at 1C for (a) an organic cell cycled between 4.3 – 1.8 V vs Na^+/Na and (b) an aqueous cell cycled between 3.4 and 2.5 V vs Na^+/Na . Comparison of the (c) discharge capacity and (d) Coulombic efficiency in both media at 1C over 50 cycles.

197 Galvanostatic Experiments in Aqueous Electrolyte. In aqueous electrolyte (1 M Na_2SO_4 ,
 198 pH = 6), the material delivered a reversible capacity of 84 mAh g^{-1} ($\Delta x = 1.95$; Figure
 199 2b,c) when tested at 1C in the voltage window 3.4 – 2.5 V vs Na^+/Na (+0.69 to –0.21 V
 200 vs SHE), with an average voltage of 3.0 V vs Na^+/Na (0.29 V vs SHE). This voltage range is
 201 slightly narrower than the theoretical one for the water stability at pH 6 (from 2.345 to
 202 3.575 V vs Na^+/Na , i.e., –0.365 to +0.865 V vs SHE)²⁸ to ensure that O_2 or H_2 evolution
 203 does not affect the cell performance. The reversible capacity value is higher than the
 204 values obtained for other iron-based polyanionic compounds tested in aqueous
 205 electrolyte at similar rates such as $\text{Na}_2\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7$ (55 mAh g^{-1})¹⁶ or NaFePO_4 (70 mAh g^{-1}),¹⁷
 206 as well as manganese-based compounds like $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ (46 mAh g^{-1})¹¹ and
 207 $\text{Na}_3\text{MnTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (58 mAh g^{-1})⁸ and thus compensates for the higher working potential of
 208 the latter ones (3.3 and 3.5 V vs Na^+/Na , i.e., 0.6 and 0.8 V vs SHE respectively).

209 The aqueous cell retained 80% of the initial capacity after 30 cycles and 74% after 50
 210 cycles (Figure 2c), which is below the capacity retention observed in the organic cell
 211 (90% after 50 cycles), and is also lower than that reported for $\text{Na}_2\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7$ (86% after 300
 212 cycles)¹⁶ and NaFePO_4 (90% after 30 cycles)¹⁷ also using 1 M $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4(\text{aq})$ as electrolyte.
 213 Interestingly, the measured overpotential (calculated as the difference between charge
 214 and discharge in the middle point of the voltage profile) is extremely low (0.07 V) and
 215 almost half the value obtained in organic electrolyte (0.13 V). A notable reduction of the
 216 overpotential was already reported for other electrode materials when cycled in
 217 aqueous cells, but the overpotential measured here is much lower than the 0.30 V
 218 measured for NaFePO_4 using the same rate and electrolyte¹⁷ and is comparable to the

219 0.05 V obtained by $\text{NaFe}_2(\text{CN})_6$,³⁵ whose structure allows an easy cation insertion and
 220 usually displays low overpotential values. Coupled with the excellent Coulombic
 221 efficiency of $\text{Na}_{4-6}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ in aqueous electrolyte ($\sim 100\%$; Figure 2d), this
 222 overpotential reduction would result in a remarkable round-trip efficiency in a full-cell.

223 EIS Study of the Overpotential Reduction. In order to gain further insight into the
 224 overpotential reduction in the aqueous electrolyte with respect to the organic
 225 electrolyte, EIS experiments were carried out. Impedance spectra were measured at the
 226 end of the charge and the discharge processes (3.4 and 2.5 V vs Na^+/Na , respectively) of
 227 the 20th, 30th, and 40th cycles in both electrolytes.

228 Figure 3a,b shows the Nyquist plots obtained in organic electrolyte, while Figure 3c,d
 229 corresponds to those in aqueous one and the corresponding galvanostatic curves are
 230 illustrated in Figure S4. The overall resistance in organic electrolyte is 2 orders of
 231 magnitude larger than that in the aqueous one, which is consistent with the difference
 232 of the respective overpotentials.
 233

234 Figure 3. Nyquist plots of the impedance spectra of $\text{Na}_{3.97-x}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ electrodes at the 20th (black), 30th (red),
 235 and 40th (blue) cycles in (a and b) organic electrolyte and (c and d) aqueous electrolyte, recorded at (a and c) 3.4 V vs
 236 Na^+/Na (0.69 V vs SHE) upon charge and at (b and d) 2.5 V vs Na^+/Na (-0.21 V vs SHE) upon discharge, respectively.
 237 The insets show the impedance data in the frequency range of (a) 101 kHz to 150 Hz, (b) 101 kHz to 40 mHz, and (c
 238 and d) 101 kHz to 100 mHz. The equivalent circuit used for the fit of the spectra and described in the main text is
 239 shown on the top of the figure.
 240

241 In both cases, the resistance increases upon cycling. The impedance data were fitted by
 242 the equivalent circuit shown on the top of Figure 3, which has been developed by
 243 Aurbach and co-workers³⁶⁻³⁸ and later modified by Barsoukov et al.^{39,40} The model
 244 gathers the different steps that Na^+ ions follow during the insertion/extraction: (i) R_{sol}

245 corresponds to the resistance of Na⁺ across the electrolyte; (ii) R_{inter} and C_{inter} connected
 246 in parallel describe the resistance and the capacitance of Na⁺ across the
 247 electrode/electrolyte interphase and appear as a semicircle at high-frequency (>1 kHz);
 248 (iii) R_{CT} corresponds to the charge-transfer resistance and C_{DL} to the formed double layer
 249 capacitance on the surface of the active particles, both connected in parallel and
 250 appearing as another semicircle at medium-frequency (1 kHz - Hz); and (iv) Z_w
 251 corresponds to the Warburg diffusion element related to the solid-state diffusion of Na⁺
 252 inside the crystal and C^i to an intercalation capacity linked to the charge accumulation,
 253 both appearing at low-frequency (mHz).⁴¹ Moreover, all capacitances and Z_w elements
 254 were replaced by constant phase elements (CPE) to take into account deviations from
 255 the ideal behavior. Table 1 shows the resistance values appearing at high- and medium-
 256 frequency obtained from the impedance data fits.

257

258 Table 1. Values of Resistances, α Value of C_{DL} and X^2 Obtained from the Fit of Impedance Spectra Using Boukamp's
 259 Software Recorded at 3.4 V vs Na⁺/Na upon charge and at 2.5 V vs Na⁺/Na upon discharge at the 20th, 30th, and
 260 40th cycles in both organic and aqueous electrolytes^a

		electrolyte			
		1 M NaClO ₄ in EC:PC		1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ (pH 6)	
		3.4 V	2.5 V	3.4 V	2.5 V
20th	R_{sol} (Ohm/mg)	2.0(0.9%)	2.1(0.9%)	0.2(3%)	0.2(3%)
	R_{inter} (Ohm/mg)	39.8(0.5%)	87.8(0.6%)	1.1(9%)	0.7(10%)
	R_{CT} (Ohm/mg)	383.3(3%)	69.1(4%)	2.1(4%)	1.5(4%)
	α_{DL}	0.8(1%)	0.9(3%)	0.9(1%)	0.9(1%)
	X^2	5.1×10^{-4}	5.2×10^{-4}	3.2×10^{-3}	3.0×10^{-3}
30th	R_{sol} (Ohm/mg)	2.1(1%)	2.2(0.9%)	0.1(3%)	0.1(3%)
	R_{inter} (Ohm/mg)	51.8(0.5%)	88.7(0.6%)	1.6(6%)	1.7(8%)
	R_{CT} (Ohm/mg)	468.3(3%)	80.4(4%)	3.0(3%)	3.0(4%)
	α_{DL}	0.8(1%)	0.9(3%)	0.9(0.5%)	0.9(0.9%)
	X^2	4.4×10^{-4}	4.8×10^{-4}	3.0×10^{-3}	4.3×10^{-3}
40th	R_{sol} (Ohm/mg)	2.1(1%)	2.2(0.8%)	0.4(2%)	0.5(3%)
	R_{inter} (Ohm/mg)	59.9(0.6%)	91.9(0.6%)	1.9(14%)	2.5(7%)
	R_{CT} (Ohm/mg)	526.0(3%)	87.7(4%)	3.4(5%)	2.8(13%)
	α_{DL}	0.8(1%)	0.9(2%)	0.9(1%)	0.9(3%)
	X^2	5.4×10^{-4}	4.3×10^{-4}	7.1×10^{-4}	7.5×10^{-4}

261

^aThe relative error is provided in parentheses.

262

263 First, R_{sol} is higher in the organic electrolyte than in the aqueous electrolyte which can
 264 be attributed to the lower ionic conductivity of 1 M NaClO₄ EC:PC (8 mS cm⁻¹)⁴²
 265 compared to the conductivity of 1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution (92 mS cm⁻¹).⁴³ Next, R_{inter}
 266 in organic electrolyte, which corresponds to the resistance of the SPI layer (Solid
 267 Permeable Interphase,⁴⁴ also often called Solid Electrolyte interphase, SEI) formed by
 268 the decomposition reactions of the electrolyte,⁴⁵ increases upon electrochemical
 269 cycling. Although the organic electrolyte decomposition reaction is not expected
 270 between 3.4 and 2.5 V vs Na⁺/Na, the formation of carbonates and alkyl-carbonates
 271 species upon reduction have already been reported for cathode materials,⁴⁶ and its
 272 presence is also here proved by the non-negligible value of R_{inter} and the XPS data shown
 273 below. Since this value increases with the cycle number, it can be concluded that the SPI
 274 layer keeps forming and/or changing upon cycling and thus that the SPI is not stable;
 275 similar behavior has been shown for other Na-based materials.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ Indeed, R_{inter} also
 276 shows higher values at the discharged states than at the charged states in organic
 277 electrolyte, probably because of the partial dissolution and reformation of additional
 278 species during oxidation and reduction processes, respectively. This is further discussed
 279 in the next section from the analysis of the XPS surface study of cycled electrodes. As
 280 regards R_{inter} in aqueous electrolyte, although its contribution is usually not
 281 observed,^{11,50,51} it was here needed to properly fit the data even if the resulting R_{inter}

282 values are very low, because the impedance spectra in aqueous medium exhibited two
283 overlapped semicircles at high/medium - frequencies. This very low resistance might
284 correspond to a passivation layer of iron oxide that is formed onto $\text{Na}_{4-x}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (0
285 $\leq x \leq 3$) active particles during cycling which would be due to the fact that the active
286 material is not completely stable in aqueous media, as discussed in the last section of
287 the paper. This passivation layer should be very thin since the R_{inter} values are very low
288 ($\leq 2.5 \Omega/\text{mg}$).

289
290 A very remarkable difference is also observed for R_{CT} , for which the values are one to
291 two orders of magnitude higher in organic electrolyte than in the aqueous one. The huge
292 difference of R_{CT} between both electrolytes has been attributed in the literature to (i)
293 the easier desolvation process of A^+ ($\text{A} = \text{Li}^+$ and Na^+) in aqueous electrolytes than in
294 organic ones^{50,51} and (ii) the better wettability of the electrode due to the lower viscosity
295 of the aqueous electrolytes.^{17,52} Indeed, He et al. have calculated the Gibbs free energy
296 for the solvating process of Li^+ in both electrolytes and the results obtained confirm that
297 the desolvation process of Li^+ in aqueous electrolyte is more facile than in organic one.⁵⁰
298 The same behavior is expected for Na^+ . We have also measured lower viscosity values
299 for the aqueous electrolyte used here (2.7 cP for 1 M Na_2SO_4 , pH 6) as compared to the
300 values reported for the organic one (5.0 cP for 1 M NaClO_4 in EC:PC). These results
301 confirm that a lower viscosity may contribute to a better soaking of the active material
302 by the aqueous electrolyte as compared to the organic one, increasing the concentration
303 of Na^+ on the surface of particles. However, our study reveals that there is in this case a
304 third factor that contributes to R_{CT} : (iii) the SPI (or SEI) layer, only formed in organic
305 electrolyte. Indeed the SPI layer acts as a blocking layer of Na^+ and hinders the diffusion
306 and migration of Na^+ from the electrolyte to the active material, which results in a
307 significant decrease of the concentration of Na^+ on the surface of the particles that are
308 involved in the deintercalation reaction and therefore in a larger R_{CT} .^{51,53} While in LIBs
309 the desolvation process has been described as the dominant contribution to the large
310 difference in R_{CT} between aqueous and organic electrolyte, the SPI layer is here shown
311 to be the main contributor to R_{CT} in organic NIBs because of two factors: first, the lower
312 energy needed to desolvate Na^+ compared to that required for Li^+ ⁵³ and, second, the
313 higher R_{inter} value measured in organic NIBs with respect to the values usually measured
314 in organic LIBs.^{50,51,54} This difference is due to the fact that the SPI (and SEI) layer in
315 organic NIBs is mainly composed by inorganic species and is more unstable upon
316 electrochemical cycling,^{47,55} while the SPI in organic LIBs is composed by organic species
317 of a few nanometers and is stable upon electrochemical cycling.⁵⁶ For all these reasons
318 it can be argued that the desolvation process is here expected to have a less important
319 contribution to R_{CT} while the contrary occurs for the SPI layer. Besides, contrary to what
320 occurs with R_{inter} , R_{CT} exhibits much larger values during Na^+ extraction (charge) than
321 during Na^+ insertion (discharge) in organic electrolyte. We believe this is due to the fact
322 that, while alkyl-carbonate and carbonate species are formed during reduction and lead
323 to an increment of R_{inter} , these species are dissolved during oxidation, creating cracks
324 and/or holes in the SPI layer. This behavior results in the exposure of the surface of the
325 active particles to the electrolyte, with their subsequent reaction. Such newly formed
326 SPI species result in a more heterogeneous and rough surface that leads to an increase
327 of R_{CT} . This hypothesis is also supported by the reduction of α during Na^+ extraction as

328 this parameter is related to the surface homogeneity and smoothness ($\alpha = 1$
329 corresponds to an ideal surface).

330 The diffusion part of the impedance, typically modeled by a Warburg element ($Z_w = Z' +$
331 jZ''), also contributes significantly to the overall resistance. The diffusive behavior in both
332 electrolytes can be more clearly observed plotting the real (Z') and imaginary ($-Z''$) parts
333 vs the frequency (Figure S5). Z' and $-Z''$ parts behave as $1/f^{1/2}$, in the low - frequency
334 region, typical of semi-infinite linear diffusion. Interestingly, Z' and $-Z''$ at 5 mHz are two
335 orders of magnitude lower in aqueous electrolyte than in organic one. The Warburg
336 impedance (Z_w) is proportional to the Warburg coefficient (A_w ; eq S1), which can be
337 determined from the Nyquist plot. The latter is in turn inversely proportional to the ionic
338 mass diffusion coefficient inside the active material D and the electroactive surface area
339 A (eq S2). Since the ionic mass diffusion only depends only on the nature of the material,
340 the origin of the difference in the Warburg impedance should come from the less
341 accessible electroactive surface area in organic electrolyte. All in all, the SPI layer is
342 responsible for the total cell impedance from 100 kHz down to 5 mHz in organic media.
343 Therefore, the overpotential reduction in aqueous electrolyte is here found to be mostly
344 related to the absence of SPI layer.

345 XPS Study of the Surface Composition. XPS experiments were carried out on electrodes
346 cycled in organic electrolyte (Figure 4a) and recovered at the charged (3.4 V vs Na^+/Na /
347 0.69 V vs SHE) and discharged (2.5 V vs Na^+/Na / -0.21 V vs SHE) states to confirm the
348 hypothesis developed from the EIS data analysis. The XPS spectra were fitted using a
349 Voigt function to quantify the amount of the different observed species (Table 2). First,
350 as the intensity of the peaks corresponding to carbon black (C-C bond; C 1s, 284.4 eV)⁵⁷
351 and the PVdF binder ($-\text{CF}_2$ bonds; F 1s, 688 eV)⁵⁸ is lower for cycled electrodes, it can be
352 concluded that a SPI layer is formed. This is in agreement with the high R_{inter} values
353 obtained from EIS data and confirms the formation of a SPI layer despite the electrolyte
354 operates inside its electrochemical stability window, as already observed in other
355 sodium-based electrode materials.^{46,47}

356
 357
 358
 359
 360
 361
 362
 363
 364
 365
 366
 367
 368
 369
 370
 371
 372
 373
 374
 375

Figure 4. C 1s (left) and F 1s (right) XPS spectra of $\text{Na}_{4-x}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 3$) electrodes (pristine, charged, and discharged states) and their deconvolution (black points correspond to experimental data and black lines to the calculated spectra) in both (a) organic and (b) aqueous electrolyte.

Second, it is shown that this SPI layer is constituted by hydrocarbon (285.7 eV), $-\text{CO}$ (286.8 eV), alkyl-carbonate (288.4 eV), carbonate (290.2 eV), and NaF (685 eV).^{45,47,56} Note that these species are usually present on the pristine electrode because of the passivation of the electrode in contact with air,^{46,47} but their amount increases after cycling. Third, the intensity of C–C (C 1s) and $-\text{CF}_2$ (F 1s) peaks is reduced at the discharged state compared to the charged state, showing that the SPI is still evolving after the first charge. This confirms that the formed SPI layer does not stabilize, as previously concluded from the variation of R_{inter} and R_{CT} values observed in the EIS experiments. This is also supported by the increase of the amount of SPI species in the C 1s spectra of the discharged electrode that corroborates that during the reduction process more species are formed. In addition, it is expected that some of them will partially dissolve during the oxidation,^{46,47} creating a more heterogeneous surface and therefore increasing R_{CT} .

Table 2. Calculated atomic percentage (at. %) of the species observed in the C 1s and F 1s spectra at charged and discharged states, as well as in the pristine electrode for both organic and aqueous electrolytes.

	binding energy (eV)	organic electrolyte			aqueous electrolyte	
		pristine	charged	discharged	pristine	charged
		C 1s				
C-C (carbon black)	284.4	42%	39%	30%	42%	44%
-CH	285.7	14%	16%	15%	14%	14%
-CH ₂ (PVdF)	286.8	7%	8%	11%	7%	6%
-CO						
NaCO ₃ R	288.4	3%	4%	8%	3%	3%
Na ₂ CO ₃	290.2	6%	8%	8%	6%	7%
		F 1s				
-CF ₂ (PVdF)	688.0	13%	12%	10%	13%	13%
NaF	685.0	0.4%	0.7%	2%	0.4%	0.4%

376

377 In contrast, the results obtained in aqueous electrolyte (Figure 4b) confirm that no SPI
378 layer is formed since the intensity and amount of all species remain constant after
379 charge (Table 2). As no new species appear during the first charge, it is expected that
380 during the subsequent discharge in the same range of potential no SPI is formed either.
381 Therefore, the XPS data confirm the hypothesis developed by EIS experiments that the
382 SPI layer is formed only in organic electrolyte and its instability upon electrochemical
383 cycling promotes a higher R_{CT} and a more sluggish ionic diffusion electrolyte.

384 Material Stability in Aqueous Electrolyte. In order to understand the larger capacity
385 fading observed in aqueous electrolyte as compared to the organic one, solubility tests
386 were carried out by immersing 100 mg of sample in 10 mL of water and in 10 mL of 1 M
387 Na₂SO₄ solution (Figure S6). After 72 h the powder was filtered and analyzed by PXRD,
388 and the recovered supernatants were analyzed by ICP. A more intense yellow color was
389 observed for the supernatant obtained from water than for the one obtained from the
390 electrolyte solution, possibly due to a higher amount of dissolved iron. The results of the
391 ICP analysis of the supernatants are gathered in Table 3.

392

393 Table 3. Results from ICP of supernatants of solubility tests of Na_{3.97}Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ described in the main text^a

394

solution	Na (at. %)	Fe (at. %)	P (at. %)	molar ratio (Na/Fe)	molar ratio (P/Fe)
water	14.2	3.5	6.0	4.1	1.74
1 M Na ₂ SO ₄		0.1	2.1		21

^aThe concentrations are expressed in atomic percentage with respect to the total amount of atoms of each element present in two different samples of 100 mg of Na_{3.97}Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ dissolved in 10 mL of water and 1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution, respectively.

395

396 The amount of sodium was quantified solely for the water solution since the electrolyte
397 already contained a high amount of Na₂SO₄ (1 M). The results show that dissolution of
398 the active material occurs in both media, although in a much lesser extent in the
399 aqueous electrolyte than in pure water. The experimental ratios of the dissolved species
400 do not have any direct relation with the stoichiometry of the compound, from which
401 one expects ideal Na/Fe and P/Fe ratios of 1.33. A possible explanation for these results
402 might be that the hydrolysis of pyrophosphates leads to iron oxides and sodium
403 phosphates, the latter being more soluble than the former.⁵⁹ Such a hypothesis is
404 confirmed, on the one hand, by the O 1s XPS spectrum of the charged electrode in

405 aqueous electrolyte which shows a peak at 530 eV corresponding to $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4^{60}$ and which
406 does not appear in the pristine electrode (see Figure S7) and, on the other hand, by the
407 presence of the small component at high frequency (R_{inter}) in the impedance spectra of
408 aqueous cells (Figure 3c,d).

409 The PXRD patterns of the powder recovered after the stability tests and their Le Bail
410 refinements are presented in Figure 5. After aging, changes in the relative intensities
411 and a slight shift of the reflections of the $\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ phase toward higher 2θ
412 angles were observed, but no new peaks from additional phases appeared except for
413 some remaining salt from the electrolyte (the contribution of NaFePO_4 is the same as
414 for the pristine sample). The refined unit cell parameters are $a = 17.833(2)$ Å, $b =$
415 $6.5080(6)$ Å, and $c = 10.717(1)$ Å for the sample aged in water and $a = 17.8860(2)$ Å, $b =$
416 $6.5292(5)$ Å, and $c = 10.711(1)$ Å for the one aged in aqueous electrolyte.

417

418

419 Figure 5. Le Bail refinements of the PXRD patterns of (a) the sample aged in water and (b) the one aged in 1 M Na_2SO_4
420 solution for 72 h. The red, black, and blue lines represent the observed pattern, calculated pattern, and difference
421 between them, respectively. The vertical bars represent the Bragg positions for $\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (green), maricite
422 NaFePO_4 (violet), and Na_2SO_4 (magenta).

423

424 From the extrapolation of the experimental cell parameters reported by Kim et al.²⁴ for
425 different x values in $\text{Na}_{4-x}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (Vegard's law), the resulting phases would
426 roughly correspond to $\text{Na}_{\sim 2.26}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ in the case of water and to
427 $\text{Na}_{\sim 2.64}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ in the case of 1 M Na_2SO_4 . The material is therefore oxidized when
428 aged, although slightly less in the case of the 1 M Na_2SO_4 electrolyte. The oxidation of
429 the material is also in agreement with the large amount of sodium found by ICP in the
430 sample recovered after the stability test in water. As a result, two chemical reactions
431 have been found to affect the cycling stability of $\text{Na}_{4-\delta}\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ in aqueous
432 electrolyte: on the one hand, hydrolysis resulting in more or less soluble species and, on
433 the other hand, oxidation of the sample during discharge process. The oxidation in
434 deoxygenated aqueous electrolyte happens below -0.365 V vs SHE (2.35 V vs Na^+/Na)
435 at the experimental pH^{28} and the O_2 evolution occurs over 0.87 V vs SHE (3.58 V vs
436 Na^+/Na), which is a higher value than the used cut off. Therefore, this phenomenon can
437 only happen due to residual and/or entrant O_2 . Even though all possible precautions

438 were taken (degasification of the electrolyte under N₂ flow, assembling in a N₂
439 atmosphere, and sealing the cell), it is difficult to ensure the total absence of oxygen.
440 Despite these secondary reactions, the excellent electrochemical properties obtained
441 for this material in aqueous electrolyte encourage the search for new approaches
442 toward their mitigation as, for example, the use of protective coatings.

443 CONCLUSIONS

444 Na₄₋₆Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ delivers a reversible capacity of 84 mAh g⁻¹ at a 1C rate in aqueous
445 electrolyte with a mean potential of 3.0 V vs Na⁺/Na. Despite working in aqueous
446 electrolyte requires using a narrowed voltage window (3.4 – 2.5 V vs Na⁺/Na), the
447 capacity obtained in the aqueous cell is almost as high as in organic electrolyte thanks
448 to the low overpotential the material exhibits in aqueous electrolyte (0.07 V). Such a low
449 overpotential is due to the contribution of three factors: (i) the easier desolvation
450 process of Na⁺ ions, (ii) the lower viscosity in aqueous electrolyte as compared to the
451 organic one, and more importantly (iii) the absence of electrolyte decomposition
452 products (SPI layer) in aqueous electrolyte, as confirmed by XPS data. The material
453 retains 74% of the initial capacity after 50 cycles. Oxidation of the active material
454 exposed to air and partial solubility in the aqueous electrolyte was observed, and further
455 work (e.g., coating of the active material) is required to circumvent these issues. If
456 successful, the good capacity, low overpotential, and good Coulombic efficiency of
457 Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇ would make it a suitable cathode for aqueous NIBs if it is combined
458 with an appropriate anode, since it exhibits a higher capacity than Na₂FeP₂O₇ and much
459 lower overpotential than NaFePO₄.

460 Author Contributions

461 Conception and design of the work: A.J.F.-R., M.Z., M.R., and M.C.-C. Synthesis and
462 structural characterization: A.J.F.-R., M.Z., and M.R. Electrochemical characterization: A
463 J.F.-R. Interphase study by EIS and XPS: M.Z. Drafting and critical revision of the article:
464 A.J.F.-R., M.Z., M.R., M.C.-C., and T.R. All authors have given approval to the final version
465 of the manuscript.

466 Notes

467 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

468 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

469 The authors would like to thank the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (MINECO)
470 of the Spanish Government for financial support through Project ENE2013-44330-R.
471 M.Z. thanks the Basque Government for her Ph.D. Fellowship. M.R. also acknowledges
472 MINECO for her postdoctoral fellowship Juan de la Cierva-Formación 2014 Reference
473 No. FJCI-2014-19990. The authors would also like to thank M. Dontigny from Institut de
474 Recherche d'Hydro-Québec (Varenes, Canada) for the viscosity measurements, B.
475 Acebedo for the elemental analysis, N. Gómez for the ICP-OES measurements, A.
476 Etxebarria for her assistance in the loading of XPS samples, and Drs. M. A. Muñoz and D.
477 Saurel for helpful discussions.

478 REFERENCES

- 479 (1) Palomares, V.; Serras, P.; Villaluenga, I.; Hueso, K. B.; Carretero-González, J.; Rojo, T.
480 Na-Ion Batteries, Recent Advances and Present Challenges to Become Low Cost Energy
481 Storage Systems. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 2012, 5, 5884–5901.
- 482 (2) Kundu, D.; Talaie, E.; Duffort, D. V.; Nazar, L. F. The Emerging Chemistry of Sodium
483 Ion Batteries for Electrochemical Energy Storage. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2015, 54,
484 3431–3448.
- 485 (3) Palomares, V.; Casas-Cabanas, M.; Castillo-Martínez, E.; Han, M. H.; Rojo, T. Update
486 on Na-Based Battery Materials. A Growing Research Path. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 2013, 6,
487 2312–2337.
- 488 (4) Whitacre, J. F.; Wiley, T.; Shanbhag, S.; Wenzhuo, Y.; Mohamed, A.; Chun, S. E.;
489 Weber, E.; Blackwood, D.; Lynch-Bell, E.; Gulakowski, J.; Smith, C.; Humphreys, D. An
490 Aqueous Electrolyte, Sodium Ion Functional, Large Format Energy Storage Device for
491 Stationary Applications. *J. Power Sources* 2012, 213, 255–264.
- 492 (5) Wu, W.; Yan, J.; Wise, A.; Rutt, A.; Whitacre, J. F. Using Intimate Carbon to Enhance
493 the Performance of $\text{NaTi}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ Anode Materials: Carbon Nanotube vs Graphite. *J.*
494 *Electrochem. Soc.* 2014, 161, A561–A567.
- 495 (6) Whitacre, J. F.; et al. A Polyanionic, Large-Format Energy Storage Device Using an
496 Aqueous Electrolyte and Thick-Format Composite $\text{NaTi}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ /Activated Carbon
497 Negative Electrodes. *Energy Technol.* 2015, 3, 20–21.
- 498 (7) Zhang, F.; Li, W.; Xiang, X.; Sun, M. Nanocrystal-Assembled Porous $\text{Na}_3\text{MgTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$
499 Aggregates as Highly Stable Anode for Aqueous Sodium Ion Batteries. *Chem. Eur. J.* 2017,
500 23, 12944–12948.
- 501 (8) Gao, H.; Goodenough, J. B. An Aqueous Symmetric Sodium-Ion Battery with NASICON
502 – Structurated $\text{Na}_3\text{MnTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2016, 55, 12768–12772.
- 503 (9) Wang, H.; Zhang, T.; Chen, C.; Ling, M.; Zhang, S.; Pan, F.; Liang, Z. High-Performance
504 Aqueous Symmetric Sodium-Ion Battery Using NASICON-structurated $\text{Na}_2\text{VTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$.
505 *Nano Res.* 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-017-1657-5>.
- 506 (10) Liu, X.; Zhang, N.; Ni, J.; Gao, L. Improved Electrochemical Performance of Sol-Gel
507 Method Prepared $\text{Na}_4\text{Mn}_9\text{O}_{18}$ in Aqueous Hybrid Na-Ion Supercapacitor. *J. Solid State*
508 *Electrochem.* 2013, 17, 1939–1944.
- 509 (11) Zhang, F.; Li, W.; Xiang, X.; Sun, M. Highly Stable Na-Storage Performance of
510 $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ Microrods as Cathode for Aqueous Sodium-Ion Batteries. *J.*
511 *Electroanal. Chem.* 2017, 802, 22–26.
- 512 (12) Wu, X.; Luo, Y.; Sun, M.; Qian, J.; Cao, Y.; Ai, X.; Yang, H. Low Defect Prussian Blue
513 Nanocubes as High Capacity and Long Life Cathodes for Aqueous Na-Ion Batteries. *Nano*
514 *Energy* 2015, 13, 117–123.
- 515 (13) Fernández-Roperro, A. J.; Piernas-Muñoz, M. J.; Castillo-Martínez, E.; Rojo, T.; Casas-
516 Cabanas, M. Electrochemical Characterization of $\text{NaFe}_2(\text{CN})_6$ Prussian Blue as Positive
517 Electrode for Aqueous Sodium-Ion Batteries. *Electrochim. Acta* 2016, 210, 352–357.
- 518 (14) Wessells, C. D.; Peddada, S. V.; McDowell, M. T.; Huggins, R. A.; Cui, Y. The Effect of
519 Insertion Species on Nanostructured Open Framework Hexacyanoferrate Battery
520 Electrodes. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 2012, 159, A98–A103.
- 521 (15) Li, W.; Zhang, F.; Xiang, X.; Zhang, X. High-Efficiency Na-Storage Performance of
522 Nickel-Based Ferricyanide Cathode in High-Concentration Electrolytes for Aqueous
523 Sodium-Ion Batteries. *ChemElectroChem* 2017, 4, 2870–2876.
- 524 (16) Jung, Y. H.; Lim, C. H.; Kim, J. H.; Kim, D. K. $\text{Na}_2\text{FeP}_2\text{O}_7$ as a Positive Electrode
525 Material for Rechargeable Aqueous Sodium-Ion Batteries. *RSC Adv.* 2014, 4, 9799–9802.

526 (17) Fernández-Ropero, A. J.; Saurel, D.; Acebedo, B.; Rojo, T.; Casas-Cabanas, M.
527 Electrochemical Characterization of NaFePO₄ as Positive Electrode in Aqueous Sodium-
528 Ion Batteries. *J. Power Sources* 2015, 291, 40–45.

529 (18) Kim, H.; Hong, J.; Park, K. Y.; Kim, H.; Kim, S. W.; Kang, K. Aqueous Rechargeable Li
530 and Na Ion Batteries. *Chem. Rev.* 2014, 114, 11788–11827.

531 (19) Nishimura, S.; Nakamura, M.; Natsui, R.; Yamada, A. New Lithium Iron
532 Pyrophosphate as 3.5 V Class Cathode Material for Lithium Ion Battery. *J. Am. Chem.*
533 *Soc.* 2010, 132, 13596–13597.

534 (20) Moreau, P.; Guyomard, D.; Gaubicher, J.; Boucher, F. Structure and Stability of
535 Sodium Intercalated Phases in Olivine FePO₄. *Chem. Mater.* 2010, 22, 4126–4128.

536 (21) Casas-Cabanas, M.; Roddatis, V. V.; Saurel, D.; Kubiak, P.; Carretero-Gonzalez, J.;
537 Palomares, V.; Serras, P.; Rojo, T. Crystal Chemistry of Na Insertion/Deinsertion in
538 FePO₄-NaFePO₄. *J. Mater. Chem.* 2012, 22, 17421–17423.

539 (22) Kawabe, Y.; Yabuuchi, N.; Kajiyama, M.; Fukuhara, T.; Inamasu; Okuyama, R.; Nakai,
540 I.; Komaba, S. Synthesis and Electrode Performance of Carbon Coated Na₂FePO₄F for
541 Rechargeable Na batteries. *Electrochem. Commun.* 2011, 13, 1225–1228.

542 (23) Kim, H.; Park, I.; Seo, D. H.; Lee, S.; Kim, S. W.; Kwon, W. J.; Park, Y. U.; Kim, C. S.;
543 Jeon, S.; Kang, K. New Iron-Based Mixed-Polyanion Cathodes for Lithium and Sodium
544 Rechargeable Batteries: Combined First Principles Calculations and Experimental Study.
545 *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2012, 134, 10369–10372.

546 (24) Kim, H.; Park, I.; Lee, S.; Kim, H.; Park, K. Y.; Park, Y. U.; Kim, H.; Kim, J.; Lim, H. D.;
547 Yoon, W. S.; Kang, K. Understanding the Electrochemical Mechanism of the New Iron-
548 Based Mixed-Phosphate Na₄Fe₃(PO₄)₂(P₂O₇) in a Na Rechargeable Battery. *Chem.*
549 *Mater.* 2013, 25, 3614–3622.

550 (25) Rodríguez-Carvajal, J. Recent Advances in Magnetic Structure Determination by
551 Neutron Powder Diffraction. *Phys. B* 1993, 192, 55–69.

552 (26) Rodríguez-Carvajal, J. FullProf Suite; 1993; <http://www.ill.eu/sites/fullprof>.

553 (27) <http://www.consultrsr.net/resources/ref/refpotls.htm>.

554 (28) Luo, J. Y.; Cui, W. J.; He, P.; Xia, Y. Y. Raising the Cycling Stability of Aqueous Lithium-
555 Ion Batteries by Eliminating Oxygen in the Electrolyte. *Nat. Chem.* 2010, 2, 760–765.

556 (29) Boukamp, B. A. A Nonlinear Least Squares Fit Procedure for Analysis of Immittance
557 Data of Electrochemical Systems. *Solid State Ionics* 1986, 20, 31–44.

558 (30) Doeff, M. M.; Ma, Y.; Visco, S. J.; De Jonghe, L. C. Electrochemical Insertion of
559 Sodium into Carbon. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 1993, 140, L169–L170.

560 (31) Komaba, S.; Murata, W.; Ishikawa, T.; Yabuuchi, N.; Ozeki, T.; Nakayama, T.; Ogata,
561 A.; Gotoh, K.; Fujiwara, K. Electrochemical Na Insertion and Solid Electrolyte Interphase
562 for Hard-Carbon Electrodes and Application to Na-Ion Batteries. *Adv. Funct. Mater.*
563 2011, 21, 3859–3867.

564 (32) Scofield, J. H. Hartree-Slater Subshell Photoionization Cross-Sections at 1254 and
565 1487 eV. *J. Electron Spectrosc. Relat. Phenom.* 1976, 8, 129–137.

566 (33) Walton, J.; Wincott, P.; Fairley, N.; Carrick, A. Peak Fitting with CasaXPS: A Casa
567 Pocket Book; Accolyte Science: Knutsford, U.K., 2010.

568 (34) Moriwake, H.; Kuwabara, A.; Fisher, C. A. J.; Nose, M.; Nakayama, H.; Nakanishi, S.;
569 Iba, H.; Ikuhara, Y. Crystal and Electronic Structure Changes During the Charge-Discharge
570 Process of Na₄Co₃(PO₄)₂P₂O₇. *J. Power Sources* 2016, 326, 220–225.

571 (35) Fernández-Ropero, A. J.; Piernas-Muñoz, M. J.; Castillo- Martínez, E.; Rojo, T.; Casas-
572 Cabanas, M. Electrochemical Characterization of NaFe₂(CN)₆ Prussian Blue as Positive
573 Electrode for Aqueous Sodium-Ion Batteries. *Electrochim. Acta* 2016, 210, 352– 357.

574 (36) Levi, M. D.; Aurbach, A. Simultaneous Measurements and Modeling of the
575 Electrochemical Impedance and the Cyclic Voltammetric Characteristics of Graphite
576 Electrodes Doped with Lithium. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 1997, 101, 4630–4640.

577 (37) Aurbach, D.; Levi, M. D.; Levi, E.; Teller, H.; Markovsky, B.; Salitra, G.; Heider, U.;
578 Heider, L. Common Electroanalytical Behavior of Li Intercalation Processes into
579 Graphite and Transition Metal Oxides. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 1998, 145, 3024–3034.

580 (38) Levi, M. D.; Salitra, G.; Markovsky, B.; Teller, H.; Aurbach, D.; Heider, U.; Heider, L.
581 Solid-State Electrochemical Kinetics of Li-ion Intercalation into Li_{1-x}CoO₂: Simultaneous
582 Application of Electroanalytical Techniques SSCV, PITT, and EIS. *J. Electrochem. Soc.*
583 1999, 146, 1279–1289.

584 (39) Barsoukov, E.; Kim, J. H.; Kim, J. H.; Yoon, C. O.; Lee, H. Kinetics of Lithium
585 Intercalation into Carbon Anodes: in Situ Impedance Investigation of Thickness and
586 Potential Dependence. *Solid State Ionics* 1999, 116, 249–261.

587 (40) Barsoukov, E.; Kim, D. H.; Lee, H. S.; Lee, H.; Yakovleva, M.; Gao, Y.; Engel, J. F.
588 Comparison of Kinetic Properties of LiCoO₂ and LiTi_{0.05}Mg_{0.05}Ni_{0.7}Co_{0.2}O₂ by
589 Impedance Spectroscopy. *Solid State Ionics* 2003, 161, 19–29.

590 (41) Barsoukov, E.; Macdonalds, J. R. *Impedance Spectroscopy. Theory, Experiment, and*
591 *Applications*, 2nd ed.; Wiley: New York, 2005.

592 (42) Ponrouch, A.; Marchante, E.; Courty, M.; Tarascon, J. M.; Palacín, M. R. In Search of
593 an Optimized Electrolyte for Na-ion Batteries. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 2012, 5, 8572–8583.

594 (43) Lota, K.; Sierczynska, A.; Acznik, I. Effect of Aqueous Electrolytes on Electrochemical
595 Capacitor Capacitance. *CHEMIK* 2013, 67, 1138–1145.

596 (44) Edström, K.; Gustafsson, T.; Thomas, J. O. The Cathode Electrode Interface in the Li-
597 Ion Battery. *Electrochim. Acta* 2004, 50, 397–403.

598 (45) Zarrabeitia, M.; Nobili, F.; Muñoz-Márquez, M. A.; Rojo, T.; Casas-Cabanas, M. Direct
599 Observation of Electronic Conductivity Transitions and Solid Electrolyte Interphase
600 Stability of Na₂Ti₃O₇ Electrodes for Na-Ion Batteries. *J. Power Sources* 2016, 330, 78–83.

601 (46) Doubaji, S.; Philippe, B.; Saadoune, I.; Gorgoi, M.; Gustafsson, T.; Solhy, A.; Valvo,
602 M.; Rensmo, H.; Edström, K. Passivation Layer and Cathodic Redox Reactions in Sodium-
603 Ion Batteries Probed by HAXPES. *ChemSusChem* 2016, 9, 97–108.

604 (47) Muñoz-Márquez, M. A.; Zarrabeitia, M.; Castillo-Martínez, E.; Eguía-Barrío, A.; Rojo,
605 T.; Casas-Cabanas, M. Composition and Evolution of the Solid-Electrolyte Interphase in
606 Na₂Ti₃O₇ Electrodes for Na-Ion Batteries; XPS and Auger Parameter Analysis. *ACS Appl.*
607 *Mater. Interfaces* 2015, 7, 7801–7808.

608 (48) Bodenes, L.; Darwiche, A.; Monconduit, L.; Martinez, H. The Solid Electrolyte
609 Interphase a Key Parameter of the High Performance of Sb in Sodium-Ion Batteries:
610 Comparative X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy Study of Sb/Na-Ion and Sb/Li-Ion
611 Batteries. *J. Power Sources* 2015, 273, 14–24.

612 (49) Baggetto, L.; Allcorn, E.; Manthiram, A.; Veith, G. M. Cu₂Sb Thin Films as Anode for
613 Na-Ion Batteries. *Electrochem. Commun.* 2013, 27, 168–171.

614 (50) He, P.; Zhang, X.; Wang, Y. G.; Cheng, L.; Xia, Y. Y. Lithium-Ion Intercalation Behavior
615 of LiFePO₄ in Aqueous and Nonaqueous Electrolyte Solutions. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 2008,
616 155, A144–A150.

617 (51) Kim, D. J.; Ponraj, R.; Kannan, A. G.; Lee, H. W.; Fathi, R.; Ruffo, R.; Mari, C. M.; Kim,
618 D. K. Diffusion Behavior of Sodium Ion in Na_{0.44}MnO₂ in Aqueous and Non-Aqueous
619 Electrolytes. *J. Power Sources* 2013, 244, 758–763.

620 (52) Park, S.; Gocheva, I.; Okada, S.; Yamaki, J. Electrochemical Properties of
621 NaTi₂(PO₄)₃ Anode for Rechargeable Aqueous Sodium-Ion Batteries. *J. Electrochem.*
622 *Soc.* 2011, 158, 1067–1070.

623 (53) Nikitina, V. A.; Fedotov, S. S.; Vassiliev, S. Y.; Samarin, A. S.; Khasanova, N. R.;
624 Antipov, E. V. Transport and Kinetic Aspects of Alkali Metal Ions Intercalation into
625 AVPO₄F Framework. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 2017, 164, A6373–A6380.

626 (54) Zhu, Y.; Xu, Y.; Luo, C.; Wang, C. S.; Liu, Y. Comparison of Electrochemical
627 Performances of Olivine NaFePO₄ in Sodium-Ion Batteries and Olivine LiFePO₄ in
628 Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Nanoscale* 2013, 5, 780–787.

629 (55) Komaba, S.; Murata, W.; Ishikawa, T.; Yabuuchi, N.; Ozeki, T.; Nakayama, T.; Ogata,
630 A.; Gotoh, K.; Fujiwara, K. Electrochemical Na Insertion and Solid Electrolyte Interphase
631 for Hard-Carbon Electrodes and Application to Na-Ion Batteries. *Adv. Funct. Mater.*
632 2011, 21, 3859–3867.

633 (56) Malmgren, S.; Ciosek, K.; Hahlin, M.; Gustafsson, T.; Gorgoi, M.; Rensmo, H.;
634 Edström, K. Comparing Anode and Cathode Electrode/Electrolyte Interface Composition
635 and Morphology Using Soft and Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy. *Electrochim.*
636 *Acta* 2013, 97, 23–32.

637 (57) Blyth, R. I. R.; Buqa, H.; Netzer, F. P.; Ramsey, M. G.; Besenhard, J. O.; Golob, P.;
638 Winter, M. XPS Studies of Graphite Electrode Materials for Lithium Ion Batteries. *Appl.*
639 *Surf. Sci.* 2000, 167, 99–106.

640 (58) Beamson, G.; Briggs, D. High Resolution XPS of Organic Polymers – The Scienta
641 ESCA300 database; Wiley Interscience: Chichester, U.K., 1992.

642 (59) Porcher, P.; Moreau, P.; Lestriez, B.; Jouanneau, S.; Guyomard, D. Is LiFePO₄ Stable
643 In Water? *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.* 2008, 11, A4–A8.

644 (60) <http://www.xpsfitting.com/search/label/Oxygen> (accessed on September 2017).